

Mapping the connectivity of higher potential naturalness areas in the UK

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Summary

A structural landscape connectivity analysis is presented with the aim of identifying areas in the UK that are conducive to ecological flow, emphasizing movement, dispersal, gene flow, and distributional range shifts for terrestrial plants and animals. The analysis uses the Land Cover Map 2020 (LCM2020) from the Centre for Ecology and Hydrology with circuit theory to model connectivity across the country. Recent advancements allow for a wall-to-wall approach, eliminating the need for pre-defined core areas. The Omniscape modelling approach, utilizing a 5km radius moving window, connects the top 30% of natural pixels, identifying areas of high permeability for multiple species.

KEYWORDS: Circuit theory, Omniscape, Connectivity, Naturalness

1. Introduction

A structural landscape connectivity analysis is presented with the aim of identifying areas in the UK that are conducive to ecological flow, emphasizing movement, dispersal, gene flow, and distributional range shifts for terrestrial plants and animals. This analysis operates at both the national and local scales, utilizing a standardized modelling approach with a specific focus on local scale permeability, which distinguishes it from conventional species-specific analyses. This work is part of an ongoing national analysis of ecological connectivity for Rewilding Britain with the intention of evaluating opportunities for improving their Rewilding Network.

The analysis uses the Land Cover Map 2020 (LCM2020) from the Centre for Ecology and Hydrology, a high-resolution classification of the UK land surface in 2020 derived from satellite images. Thematic spatial layers are created based on potential naturalness and human influence on the landscape. The former classifies areas such as broadleaf woodlands with higher scores, while the latter focuses on distance to roads and built density as proxies for human influence. These layers are reclassified and combined into a 'resistance surface' at a pixel resolution of 100m x 100m.

2. Methods

Circuit theory is used to model connectivity across a fine resolution landscape scale dataset. Recent advancements allow for a wall-to-wall approach, eliminating the need for pre-defined core areas. The Omniscape modelling approach, utilizing a 5km radius moving window, connects the top 30% of natural pixels, identifying areas of high permeability for multiple species as shown in Figure 1. In the simplest case, a moving window is passed over the resistance and source weight rasters (see Figure 2) centering in turn on each pixel. If the centre pixel meets the naturalness criteria for being a destination for movement, it is treated as a target for movement. All pixels within the moving window radius that meet the same criteria are considered as sources. Current flows from all source pixels to the target pixel, with more current flowing from more natural source pixels.

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Figure 1. Illustration of the moving window method in Omniscape

Figure 2. Resistance and core areas.

3. Results

Results are presented in three spatial layers: cumulative current flow, flow potential, and normalized cumulative current flow. These layers highlight areas of higher permeability, bottlenecks to movement, and the mechanisms behind different flow rates. The normalization of current flow by flow potential helps distinguish areas with diffuse flow from those with barriers (see Figure 3).

The analysis assumes that areas with higher potential naturalness support a larger number of native species and maintain intact ecological processes. Well-connected areas with higher naturalness potential are believed to be more ecologically intact. This aligns with landscape conservation planning principles emphasizing the importance of a connected landscape network supporting diverse species and habitat types. Data constraints include the absence of equivalent data for scrub or meadows, limited national-scale data on the ecological integrity of water bodies, and reliance on remotely sensed datasets without ground-level validation. The moving window approach has limitations in distinguishing local pinch-points from more intact portions of the study area. Interpretation complexities arise from the interplay of natural land configuration and movement route availability.

Figure 3. Flow potential and ecological current flow.

4. Discussion

The draft assessment serves as a preliminary analysis to identify well-connected areas of higher potential naturalness. It highlights areas of higher permeability between larger intact areas and can be

further analysed using graph theory to identify nationally significant stepping stones and gaps in the current protected area network. The iterative process involves integrating local-scale ecological data and other social considerations. Similar mapping approaches are being employed in two French regions by the French Botanical Institute of the Alps to identify potential intact natural areas for future protection. The second stage of analyses involves ground truthing exercises and quantitative assessments using graph theory, providing a more structured interpretation of the results.

The outputs are currently undergoing ground truthing exercises, particularly in the south coast of England and the North York Moors National Park area. In parallel to expert ground truthing, a quantitative analysis is also demonstrated using graph theory. This provides metrics to describe the relative importance of the areas of high ecological flow and connecting landscape linkages in the overall network of patches and corridors. This structured approach allows for a more nuanced interpretation and presentation of the results, comparing the importance of patches and corridors at local and national scales.

We conclude that this draft landscape connectivity analysis provides valuable insights into potential areas of interest for ecological flow in the UK. Acknowledging its limitations, the iterative nature of the process ensures a comprehensive and informed approach to landscape conservation planning. The second stage analyses contribute depth and structure to the interpretation of results, paving the way for more targeted conservation strategies.

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Biographies

Steve Carver has over 30 years' experience in using and developing GIS models in spatial analysis and environmental modelling. He has built an international reputation in applying these to wilderness, wild land and rewilding problems across the world including Scotland, the UK, France, Iceland, Europe, the USA, Mexico, and China.

Jonathan Carruthers-Jones has worked on mapping connectivity and wilderness for over a decade. He has experience of working on large scale connectivity conservation projects such as the Great Mountain Corridor project. He was Postdoctoral Research Fellow on the 'Where are the wild things?', Arctic Interactions Project, University of Oulu, Finland. He is a member of the IUCN-WCPA Mountains Biome Network and a member of the wilderness working group of French IUCN 'Wilderness et nature férale' where he has recently led work on the first wilderness map of France.